

Towards Green Cities: The Impact of Bus-Priority Lanes on Emission Control for Highly Congested Metropolitan Areas During Peak Times

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Abstract. This study evaluates public transport accessibility in Lima, Peru, and assesses the potential impact of implementing bus priority lanes. Using multimodal network modeling and open-source data, accessibility to points of interest is compared across different travel scenarios. Results highlight significant gaps in Lima's current system and demonstrate how targeted infrastructure improvements can enhance access, reduce car dependency, and support sustainable urban mobility.

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vere traffic congestion, poor air quality, and fragmented, largely informal public transport services (Cabello-Torres et al., 2024). While these conditions present challenges, they also offer an opportunity to shift urban mobility toward sustainability before car dependency becomes entrenched. This study assesses the accessibility to points of interest (POI) provided by Lima's current public transport system and evaluates how specific interventions—namely, the implementation of bus-priority lanes—could enhance accessibility and reduce car dependency. Accessibility is measured by comparing multimodal travel (walking combined with bus use) to car travel during peak traffic hours. The study focuses on identifying regions where improvements in PT infrastructure, particularly the addition of bus priority lanes, would yield the most significant benefits. For comparison and additional insight, London's public transport system, which similarly faces challenges with traffic congestion, is also analyzed. Its comprehensive and openly accessible data enable an in-depth analysis and provide valuable insights for cities in the Global North.

1 Introduction

Public transport (PT) is crucial for sustainable urban development, especially in metropolitan areas, which are major contributors to global greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. The transportation sector is responsible for 23% of global energy-related CO₂ emissions, 70% of which come from road vehicles (Jaramillo et al., 2022). As urban populations grow and car ownership increases, particularly in developing regions, there is an urgent need to shift travel demand to more sustainable modes such as public transport (Mulley et al., 2016). Bus Rapid Transit (BRT) systems and bus priority lanes, as seen in cities such as Mexico City, demonstrate the potential of cost-effective solutions to improve urban mobility and reduce emissions (Bel and Holst, 2018). Lima, Peru, presents a particularly relevant case. Despite relatively low car ownership compared to other cities of similar size, Lima suffers from se-

2 Data and Methods

To assess accessibility, walking and driving isochrones were calculated using OpenRouteService (ORS), modeling areas reachable within 1 to 30 minutes. A multimodal transportation network was constructed by integrating pedestrian routes, bus travel edges derived from GTFS data created from official government data, and transfer connections. Three travel scenarios were analyzed: a nominal network based on scheduled bus travel times, a rush-hour network that simulated reduced bus speeds and delays, and a priority lane network that applied higher speeds to feasible priority lane segments while maintaining rush-hour conditions elsewhere. The feasibility of implementing bus priority lanes was assessed by analyzing road segments from OpenStreetMap (OSM) data extracted by us-

ing the ohsome API. Roads with four or more lanes (or two lanes on one-way streets) were considered suitable for priority lanes. For each modeled scenario, the number of accessible POI within a 30-minute travel window was computed, and a Normalized Difference POI Count (NDPC) index was used to compare accessibility via car and multimodal travel. Spatial clustering of accessibility improvements was analyzed using Local Moran's I, with district-level car ownership data derived from government data overlaid to examine potential socio-economic impacts. Road and POI data were extracted from OpenStreetMap (OSM) using the ohsome API (Raifer et al., 2019). A snippet of the data and scripts used for this work can be found at <https://github.com/GIScience/busability-lima-agile-2025>.

3 Results

The results show significant gaps in the accessibility of public transport in Lima. Only 49.1% of bus stops are accessible within a six-minute walk, a figure that drops sharply to 12.8% when only formal bus lines are considered. Peripheral neighborhoods often require walking times exceeding 30 minutes to reach the nearest bus stop, falling short of the Sustainable Development Goal 11 target of a 500-meter maximum walking distance to public transport (United Nations Statistics Division, 2024). The implementation of bus priority lanes leads to a significant increase in accessibility, with a 28.6% increase in the number of POI reachable within 30 minutes. Spatial clustering highlights that central and eastern areas of Lima, such as San Juan de Lurigancho, benefit most from improved accessibility. These areas also have lower car ownership rates, suggesting that infrastructure investments here could meaningfully reduce future car dependency. In contrast, 95.7% of bus stops in London are within a six-minute walking distance. The NDPC values in London remain consistent across the different scenarios.

4 Discussion

The analysis highlights the potential of bus priority lanes to improve PT accessibility in Lima, especially in underserved areas. The formalization of informal transit services is equally important. The transition from semi-formal to formal transit, is necessary to ensure safety, reliability, and lower emissions. The study also highlights the importance of improving data quality, especially in the Global South, where incomplete records of informal transit services limit the accuracy of accessibility models.

By demonstrating how open-source data and spatial network analysis can highlight accessibility gaps and opportunities for intervention, this study offers a transferable workflow applicable to other cities facing similar challenges. Lima's relatively low car ownership offers a crit-

ical window of opportunity to invest in public transport infrastructure that is equitable and sustainable. Expanding bus networks, prioritizing bus lanes, and integrating informal transit services could significantly enhance accessibility, reduce congestion, and lower GHG emissions.

Future research should focus on validating these modeled results with real-world usage data, incorporating user behavior insights, and refining transit parameters. Enhancing data availability and accuracy, especially concerning informal transit operations, will be key to supporting effective, sustainable public transport strategies in Lima and similar urban environments worldwide.

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